

Two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband transmit/receive switch

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ABSTRACT

This article introduces a broadband microstripline-based transmit/receive switch for 7-Tesla magnetic resonance imaging. The designed switch aims to handle a signal of multiple frequencies to/from a multi-tuned radio-frequency coil that resonates at frequencies corresponding to the speed of precession of a wide range of atomic X-nuclei, at the same time and without tuning. These include ¹H, ²³Na, ¹³C, ³¹P, ¹⁹F, and ⁷Li used in magnetic resonance spectroscopy as a measure to the existence of many diseases. The fundamental and third harmonic center frequencies of the switch are adjusted to resonate at two broadbands covering a wide range of atomic X-nuclei. Two section branch-line hybrid couplers with phase inverters are designed to build the broadband switch. The designed switch used the minimum trace widths of transmission lines that reveal a compact size without increasing the heat and then the loss beyond specific values. The couplers and the switch S-parameters exhibited good return loss (<-10 dB), high isolation (<-40 dB), less insertion loss (<1 dB) and two clear wide bands covering many atomic X-nuclei used in diagnosis, at the same time and without the need for any tuning circuit during operation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Transmit/receive (T/R) switches in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are essential elements when T/R radio frequency (RF) coils are used. They are located between the RF amplifier and the RF coils. The long cables between the power amplifier and the coil as well as the T/R switches add loss to the RF transmitting chain of magnetic for MRI scanner, and thus effect on the power delivered to the transmit coil and increase the noises. The cable loss is reduced by designing power amplifiers of nonmagnetic components near to the magnet bore [1]. Another approach is to design T/R switches that satisfy low insertion loss, high isolation, and good return loss. For single resonant frequency coils, such as ¹H protons RF coils, the same single resonance signal must be handled by the switch to the RF coil during transmit and from the coil to the receiver during receive. Similarly, dual and multi resonance T/R RF coils need dual and multi tuned T/R switches, respectively.

Magnetic resonance imaging and spectroscopy (MRI/MRS) can provide images with anatomical and metabolic information of the human [2]–[5]. Several studies have shown that non-proton (X-) nuclear imaging can provide valuable information from tissues [6], [7]. For example, ²³Na imaging can examine multiple sclerosis and tumors [8], [9]. ³¹P imaging has been used for assessing healthy human brain, examine breast

cancer and providing complementary information on the biology of prostate cancer [10]–[12]. In this context, several dual-nuclear RF coils have been developed for ultra-high field MRI. In [13], multi-channel $^1\text{H}/^{31}\text{P}$ RF coil for 7T MRI has been presented. The coil has been designed using a four-channel dipole array for ^1H imaging and a four-channel loop array for ^{31}P imaging. In [14], a $^1\text{H}/^{23}\text{Na}$ RF coil has been presented. This coil is designed using monopole, for ^1H imaging, crossing the center of the loop coil, which is used for ^{23}Na imaging.

In the literature, various types of switches have been designed. PIN diodes-based T/R switches are introduced to satisfy high reliability, power handling, linearity [15]–[18]. The switching time from transmit to receive was revealed within $0.4 \mu\text{s}$ and from receive to transmit reached within $2 \mu\text{s}$ [16]. Transistors-based T/R switches are introduced in [19], [20]. The enhanced mode eGaN FETs in [16] showed an advantage over PIN diodes in B0 and B1 homogeneity and the amount of biased power to work, but it revealed less image SNR. Micro electromechanical system (MEMS) based switches [21], [22] were designed and compared to topologies based on PIN diodes and they showed higher isolation, and lower DC switching voltage. These switches have not been broadly used in MRI applications.

A novel microstripline (MSL) based T/R switches, for ^1H protons 7-Tesla MRI, have been designed and introduced in [23]. In that work, we introduced two switches of unsymmetrical and symmetrical hybrid couplers topologies and compared their results with a third commercial coupler switch from the market. The measurements showed that the MSL-based switches are better in terms of heat dissipation, handling higher power, and have less insertion loss. We introduced new MSL-based T/R switches with different topologies and realistic trace widths to handle the RF pulses to/from ^1H RF coils working at 298 MHz, the operating frequency at 7-Tesla MRI [24]. The introduced switch achieves a compact design with minimum dimensions and without increasing the temperature 20 degree Celsius beyond the ambient temperature. Dual tuned MSL-based T/R switches have also been introduced to work properly with dual resonance RF coils to interrogate different X-nuclei [25]. Our proposed and introduced microstripline-based switches can handle the RF pulses, with very low insertion loss, as well as good return loss and isolation, to/from single and dual tuned RF coils.

In this article, a new broadband MSL-based T/R switch is designed to handle RF pulses of multiple resonances to/from multi-tuned RF coils, at the same time and without tuning. These resonances are falling within two broadbands where the speed of various X-nuclei (such as ^1H , ^{23}Na , ^{13}C , ^{31}P , ^7Li , ^{19}F) exist. The targeted atomic X-nuclei are used in magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) as a measure to the existence of many diseases. The objective of this work is to achieve this broadband design, reduce the insertion loss, minimize the size while keeping the realistic design constraints of trace widths and its allowable maximum acceptable temperature.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The two-section branch-line broadband hybrid coupler has been originally presented in [26]. It consists of three vertical transmission lines (a,c,a) and four horizontal transmission lines (b,b,b,b) as shown in Figure 1. An inverter (180° phase shifter) has been inserted at the middle vertical transmission line to enhance the bandwidth. The length for all the transmission lines is the same and equal to quarter wavelength.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the two-section branch-line hybrid coupler

The scattering matrix of this hybrid coupler has been derived in [27], and can be presented as (1):

$$\begin{pmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & S_{13} & S_{14} \\ S_{21} & S_{22} & S_{23} & S_{24} \\ S_{31} & S_{32} & S_{33} & S_{34} \\ S_{41} & S_{42} & S_{43} & S_{44} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\sqrt{\left(\frac{k}{k+1}\right)} & 0 & -j\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{k+1}\right)} \\ -\sqrt{\left(\frac{k}{k+1}\right)} & 0 & -j\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{k+1}\right)} & 0 \\ 0 & -j\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{k+1}\right)} & 0 & -\sqrt{\left(\frac{k}{k+1}\right)} \\ -j\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{k+1}\right)} & 0 & -\sqrt{\left(\frac{k}{k+1}\right)} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where “ k ” is the ratio of the signal power at the through port to the signal power at the coupled port, and can be expressed as (2):

$$k = \left| \frac{S_{21}}{S_{41}} \right|^2 = \frac{Z_o^2 Z_c^2}{Z_b^2} \quad (2)$$

where Z_c and Z_b are the characteristic impedances for transmission lines “ c ” and “ b ”, respectively. To calculate these impedances together with the characteristic impedances for the transmission line “ a ” (Z_a), we can use (3) and (4):

$$Z_a = (\sqrt{k} + \sqrt{k+1})Z_o \quad (3)$$

$$Z_c = \frac{\sqrt{k}Z_b^2}{Z_o} \quad (4)$$

In order to obtain the quadrature hybrid coupler with -3 dB output ports, the ratio “ k ” should be equal to 1. In this case, the input RF signal is inserted into port 1. Port 2 (through) and port 4 (coupled) are the -3 dB quadrature outputs. Port 3 is the isolated port. Now, if we assume $Z_b=Z_o$, then Z_c will be equal to Z_o from (4), and Z_a will be equal to $2.414 Z_o$ from (3). This hybrid coupler has been designed on Rogers substrate RO 4,725 with relative permittivity 2.55 and thickness of 1.542 mm using ADS software, as shown in Figure 2. The dimensions of the final design are 400×180 mm.

Figure 2. Layout of the two-section branch-line hybrid coupler

In order to build-up the broadband T/R switch using the two-section branch-line hybrid couplers, the connections shown in Figure 3 have been applied. If we imagine a virtual line between the two couplers acting as a mirror, then the two hybrid couplers are connected to each other at two ports: the through ports and the coupled ports. At transmit, the two PIN diodes which are connected at through and coupled ports of the first coupler (left), are forward biased. In this case, all the input signals will be delivered to the RF coil at port 2. At receiving, both PIN diodes are reverse biased and the detected RF signal from the RF coil at port 2 will be delivered to port 4.

Figure 3. Two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband T/R switch

Two short coaxial cables are used to operate as inverters at the middle transmission line of each coupler. A 180° phase shift can be achieved using coaxial cable once the straight connection is replaced by a crossover connection as shown in Figure 4. The first coaxial cable is inserted between ports 9 and 10 whereas the second coaxial cable is inserted between ports 11 and 12.

Figure 4. The broadband T/R switch in CST showing the connections of ports and the two inverters (cross connected coaxial cables)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The designed two-section branch-line hybrid couplers as shown in Figure 2 characterized by two broadbands appear at the fundamental frequency and the third odd harmonics, as shown in Figure 5. This Figure demonstrates good return loss and isolation. The bandwidths of the first and second broadband were

falling in the ranges 75-135 MHz and 293-334 MHz. These broad bandwidths have been specified based on the definition of the coupling imbalance between the two output ports (through and coupled) that must be better than 0.86 dB (3.0 ± 0.43 dB) [28].

Figure 5. S-parameters for the two-section branch-line hybrid couplers

To evaluate the performance of the proposed two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband T/R switch, S-parameters have been obtained from CST. At transmit, good matching ($S_{11} < -10$ dB) and low insertion loss ($S_{21} < -1$ dB) have been obtained at all atomic nuclei resonance frequencies, as shown in Figure 6 and Table 1. In addition, high isolation ($S_{41} < -40$ dB) between transmitter and receiver can be obtained.

Figure 6. S-parameters at transmit phase for two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband T/R switch

Table 1. S-parameters for two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband T/R switch at transmit phase

Atomic Nuclei	Frequency (MHz)	S11 (dB)	S21 (dB)	S41 (dB)
¹³ C	75.0	-23.2	-0.25	-50
²³ Na	78.8	-28.7	-0.26	-48
⁷ Li	115.8	-22.6	-0.38	-45
³¹ P	120.6	-32.1	-0.35	-44
¹⁹ F	280.4	-11.2	-0.92	-42
¹ H	298.0	-13.0	-0.74	-42

At receiving, good matching ($S_{22} < -13$ dB) and low insertion loss ($S_{21} < -0.9$ dB) have been obtained at all atomic nuclei resonance frequencies, as shown in Figure 7 and Table 2. It is worth mentioning that the first operating band of the T/R switch is extended from 66.2–147.3 MHz. Whereas the second operating band is extended from 279.6–352.2 MHz. Within these two bands, an insertion loss is lower than 1 dB and the return loss is at least 10 dB can be obtained at both transmit and receive modes.

Figure 7. S-parameters at receive for two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband T/R switch

Table 2. S-parameters for two-section branch-line hybrid couplers based broadband T/R switch at receive phase

Atomic Nuclei	Frequency (MHz)	S22 (dB)	S24 (dB)
^{13}C	75.0	-33.6	-0.15
^{23}Na	78.8	-37.1	-0.12
^7Li	115.8	-14.1	-0.37
^{31}P	120.6	-17.8	-0.26
^{19}F	280.4	-30.0	-0.83
^1H	298.0	-13.6	-0.61

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, a transmit/receive switch is designed to handle a broadband signal of operating frequencies to/from multi-tuned radio-frequency coil working at 7-Tesla MRI. The two-section branch-line method is used from transmission line theory to design two stacked microstripline-based hybrid couplers of two broadband signals covering many atomic X-nuclei. The couplers and then the switch have been designed using ADS and MW-CST. The broadband couplers have been designed with an excellent coupling imbalance between the two output ports, (3.0 ± 0.43 dB), that satisfies bandwidth of 75–135 MHz and 293–334 MHz. The proposed broadband T/R switch achieved good matching ($S_{11} < -10$ dB) and low insertion loss ($S_{21} < -1$ dB) at transmit, and high isolation ($S_{41} < -40$ dB) between transmitter and receiver. At receiving, the switch revealed good matching ($S_{22} < -13$ dB) and low insertion loss ($S_{21} < -0.9$ dB). These values have achieved at two wide bandwidths of operating frequencies (from 66.2 to 147.3 MHz and from 279.6 to 352.2 MHz.) covering many atomic X-nuclei including the ^{32}Na , ^{31}P , ^{13}C , ^{19}F , ^7Li and others as well as the ^1H . These bandwidths have been calculated based on achieving an insertion loss less than 1 dB and a return loss better than 10 dB. Our broadband switch can work with any single or multi-tuned RF coil that resonates at frequency inside the two bandwidths of the switch. One can change the coil without changing the switch. A dual tuned $^1\text{H}/\text{X}$ -Nuclei or multi-tuned RF coil can be used with the same switch without any type of tuning. The introduced switch is a promising economical solution and can be used to minimize the needed space of T/R switches when multi-channel multi-tuned RF coils become widely available.

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